

PENINGKATAN KEMAMPUAN GURU DALAM MENYUSUN PERANGKAT PEMBELAJARAN MENGGUNAKAN METODE SUPERVISI AKADEMIK

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Abstrak

Penelitian dilakukan untuk meningkatkan kemampuan guru mata pelajaran dalam menyusun rencana pelaksanaan pembelajaran (RPP) dan lembar kerja siswa (LKPD) menggunakan metode supervisi terhadap guru mata pelajaran. Jenis penelitian adalah penelitian tindakan sekolah melalui supervisi akademik. Subjek penelitian adalah sepuluh guru di SMP Negeri 4 Pontianak. Penilaian dilakukan dengan mengisi instrumen penilaian kompetensi profesional guru melalui supervisi akademik. Hasil supervisi akademik untuk meningkatkan kemampuan guru mata pelajaran dalam menyusun RPP dan LKPD melalui supervisi dan refleksi tergambar dari hasil pengamatan selama dua siklus. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa kompetensi profesional guru dalam menyusun RPP dan LKPD serta pelaksanaan proses pembelajaran mengalami peningkatan melalui supervisi akademik pada kategori baik.

Kata Kunci: supervisi akademik; kompetensi profesional; perangkat pembelajaran.

Abstract

This research aimed to improve the ability of ten teachers in preparing lesson plans (RPP) and student worksheets (LKPD) using the supervision method for subject teachers. The type of research conducted was school action research through academic supervision. The subjects in this research were ten teachers of SMP Negeri 4 Pontianak. The assessment was carried out by filling out the instrument for assessing the professional competence of subject teachers' academic supervision. The results of academic supervision to improve the ability of subject teachers in preparing RPP and LKPD through supervision and reflection were illustrated by the results of observations for two cycles. The professional competence of teachers in preparing RPP and LKPD as well as the implementation of the learning process as increased through academic supervision in the good category.

Keywords: *academic supervision; professional competence; learning media.*